

Introduction

When I first moved to Germany, my father suggested playing billiards together to break the monotony of my daily life. Since I have a strong interest in mathematics, I was thrilled when I discovered that I could calculate the precise path and angle, hit the ball, and score exactly as I intended. As I continued playing the sport, I began to question why the trajectories and paths of the ball seemed slightly different each time even when hitting the balls with the same setup, force, and angle. This made me curious whether other factors beyond just the force and angle of the shot—such as the point of contact on the ball—could also influence its direction. I wanted to study the trajectory of billiard balls mathematically, and eventually, I hoped to simulate it using basic coding.

Method

1. Physics Equations

To simulate the movement of billiard balls, I first utilized simple physics equations that describe the motion of objects:

$$V_x = V_{x0} - a_x t = 0$$

$$V_y = V_{y0} - a_y t = 0$$

$$S = \sqrt{V_x^2 + V_y^2}$$

$$S = V_0 t + 0.5 a t^2$$

2. Simulation / Coding Method

To calculate the trajectory of the billiard balls, I divided the movement into three cases:

- 1) when balls collide with each other
- 2) when a ball hits a wall
- 3) when a ball comes to a stop without hitting anything.

For each case, I identified which equations could be applied and organized the process into a flowchart to plan the steps in detail. Once the necessary steps became clear, I transferred the flowchart into Google Colab and implemented it in code to simulate the movement of the balls.

3. Flowchart

To carry out the basic tasks, I first studied what a “flowchart” is. A flowchart, also called a process diagram or sequence diagram, represents a process using simple symbols and shapes. To become familiar with flowcharts, I first practiced with various examples, such as the Fibonacci sequence. After that, I visualized the movement of billiard balls by breaking the process down into different cases and representing each case in a diagram.

Figure 1. Example of flowchart

4. Vectors

A vector is a quantity that has both magnitude and direction. I intended to use vectors to calculate the collision times of balls moving in different directions. For example, if the basic conditions, such as the angle at which a billiard ball hits a wall, are known, it should be possible

to calculate when the ball will stop and at what velocity it will rebound. Specifically, by decomposing the force into its horizontal and vertical components based on the angle of impact and applying the concept of vector projection, these calculations could be performed more easily.

Figure 2. Example of vectors

5. Mathematical Knowledge

While simulating collisions between balls using both vectors and physics, I encountered quartic equations that are generally difficult to solve by hand. Although finding a general solution to a quartic equation without factoring is challenging at an advanced level, computers can solve them easily. Therefore, I incorporated this into the coding process so that the computer could handle the calculations.

6. Approximating Parts Beyond High School-Level Mathematics

During the simulation, I frequently encountered aspects that could not be solved using high school-level mathematics. For example, this simulation excluded ball rotation, did not account for the difference between a perfectly hit ball and a glancing hit, and could not represent the sliding of the ball immediately after being struck. To make the simulation more realistic, I looked for ways to approximate these phenomena as closely as possible, even if not perfectly.

To incorporate ball rotation, I simplified it into a function based on two key factors: the point of contact on the ball and the force of the strike. This part is discussed in more detail in the Discussion section.

While studying flowcharts, I practiced breaking down examples such as the Fibonacci sequence into conditional statements and commands, following the proper flowchart format. One example of the result was as follows.

I also drew flowcharts for various other topics. Once I became sufficiently familiar, I moved on

to planning the coding for the billiard simulation.

$W=X$ $PI(W,R,Y)$ $PF(W,R,Y)$
 $H=Y$ $VI(W,R,Y)$ $VF(W,R,Y)$
 $A_{W,R,Y}$

- ① $V_W \neq 0$ $V_R = 0$ $V_Y = 0$ 2, 3, 6, 8, 9 제외
 ↳ W-벽
- ② $V_W \neq 0$ $V_R = 0$ $V_Y \neq 0$ 2, 3, 6, 8, 9 제외
 ↳ W-R
- ③ $V_W \neq 0$ $V_R \neq 0$ $V_Y = 0$ 3, 9 제외
 ↳ R-벽
- ④ $V_W \neq 0$ $V_R \neq 0$ $V_Y \neq 0$
 ↳ R-Y
- ⑤ $V_W \neq 0$ $V_R = 0$ $V_Y \neq 0$
 ↳ W=0
- ⑥ $V_W = 0$ $V_R \neq 0$ $V_Y \neq 0$
 ↳ R=0
- ⑦ $V_W = 0$ $V_R = 0$ $V_Y \neq 0$ 1, 2, 4, 7, 8 제외
 ↳ V_Y=0
- ⑧ $V_W = 0$ $V_R = 0$ $V_Y \neq 0$ 1, 2, 4, 7, 8 제외
 ↳ Y-R
- ⑨ $V_W = 0$ $V_R \neq 0$ $V_Y \neq 0$ → W-R 1, 7 제외

- ① $V_{Ball} = 0$: $V_F = V_I + at$
 $t = \frac{|V_I|}{|a|}$
 $PF = PI + V_I t - \frac{1}{2} at^2$
- ② Ball-Ball (W-R, W-Y, R-Y)
 $\frac{1}{2}(A_{W-R})^2 t^2 + (V_{R2} - V_{W2})t + PI_R - PI_W = 0$
 $t = ?$ (non-candidate)
 $PF_{Ball} = PI_{Ball} + V_I t - \frac{1}{2} at^2$
- ③ Ball-Wall (W-wall, R-wall, Y-wall)
 $PI_{Ball} + V_I t - \frac{1}{2} at^2 = 0, X, Y$
 $t = ?$
 $\Rightarrow PF_{Ball} = PI_{Ball} + V_I t - \frac{1}{2} at^2$

Case 1, 2, 3
X, Y

All V=0

Yes

No

I divided the simulation into three cases mentioned in Section 2, and for each case, I established the corresponding physics equations and performed the calculations. By doing this, I set up the foundation for coding through flowcharts, and the final coded simulation produced the following results:

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

import numpy as np

import math

# Billiard table width and height (cm)

W = 1.422*100 # (1) TODO : Set table width

H = 2.844*100 # (2) TODO : Set table height

# Ball radius (cm)

r = 0.061*100 # (3) TODO : Set ball radius # COMMENT: Doesn't the ball look too large?

# Define infinity

inf = 9999999999999999

# Acceleration due to friction

a = 2*100 # (4) TODO : Set ball acceleration (not exact, adjust based on results)

# Deceleration after collision

K_ball_ball_col = 0.95

K_ball_wall_col = 0.75

#Considering contact point

N = 0.1 # theta = N * (sqrt(d))

M = 1 # thata = M * d**2 * (1/s)
```

```
class Ball:

    def __init__(self, px, py, vx, vy, d, color):

        # Define the properties of the ball at each moment

        # Mass, color, etc

        self.px = px

        self.py = py

        self.vx = vx

        self.vy = vy

        self.d = d

        self.color = color

        # (5) TODO : Explain the role of the following lines

        self.px_log = [px]

        self.py_log = [py]

    def __str__(self):

        return(f" {self.color} : ({self.px:.4f}, {self.py:.4f}) / ({self.vx:.4f}, {self.vy:.4f})")

    def move(self, t):

        # Where will the ball be after t seconds, and at what speed?

        # Retrieve values (for convenience)

        px = self.px
```

```

py = self.py

vx = self.vx

vy = self.vy

d = self.d

# Speed magnitude
s = (vx ** 2 + vy ** 2) ** 0.5

if d != 0:

    # Recalculate velocity components based on contact point
    theta = N*abs(d)**(0.5) * d/abs(d)

    tan_theta = math.tan(theta)

    if vx != 0:

        tan_original = vy/vx

        tan_revised = (tan_original - tan_theta) / (1 + tan_original * tan_theta)

        vx = s / (1 + tan_revised**2)**0.5

        vy = s * tan_revised / (1 + tan_revised**2)**0.5

    if vx == 0:

        vx = math.sin(theta) * s

        vy = math.cos(theta) * s

if s == 0:

```

```
    return

# Vectorize acceleration

ax = a * (vx / s)

ay = a * (vy / s)

px = px + vx * t - 0.5 * ax * t ** 2

py = py + vy * t - 0.5 * ay * t ** 2

vx = vx - ax*t

vy = vy - ay*t

self.px = px

self.py = py

self.vx = vx

self.vy = vy

self.d = 0

# (6) TODO : Explain the role of the following lines

self.px_log.append(px)

self.py_log.append(py)

# Test run

print("-----")

ball_test = Ball(4,3,2,1, 0.5,"white")
```

```

ball_test.move(1)

print(ball_test.px, ball_test.py)

print(ball_test.vx, ball_test.vy)

print("-----")

ball_test = Ball(4,3,2,1, -0.9,"white")

ball_test.move(1)

print(ball_test.px, ball_test.py)

print(ball_test.vx, ball_test.vy)

def min_root_from_eq_with_range(coef, max_x):

    eps = 1e-9

    # Function to calculate roots of higher-order polynomials

    roots = np.roots(coef)

    candidates = [r.real for r in roots

                   if abs(r.imag) < eps and 0 < r.real < max_x + eps]

    return min(candidates) if candidates else inf

def time_stop(ball): # When does this ball stop?

    vx = ball.vx

    vy = ball.vy

```

```

# Norm of velocity, speed, hypotenuse for trigonometry

s = (vx ** 2 + vy ** 2) ** 0.5

# v - a*t = 0 => t = v / a (vector case)

t = s / a

return t

# Test code

ball_test = Ball(1,1,1,0, 0.5, "white")

print(time_stop(ball_test))

ball_test = Ball(1,1, 0.54561321, 0.515612, -0.2, "white")

print(time_stop(ball_test))

def time_to_wall_collision(ball): # When does the ball collide with a wall?

# For x-axis movement: collision at x = 0+r or W-r

# For y-axis movement: collision at y = 0+r or H-r

# X-axis components

px = ball.px

vx = ball.vx

py = ball.py

vy = ball.vy

```

```
d = ball.d
```

```
# Norm of velocity, speed, hypotenuse for trigonometry
```

```
s = (vx ** 2 + vy ** 2) ** 0.5
```

```
if d != 0:
```

```
# Recalculate velocity components based on contact point
```

```
theta = N*abs(d)**(0.5) * d/abs(d)
```

```
print("angle : ", theta * 180 / 3.14)
```

```
tan_theta = math.tan(theta)
```

```
if vx != 0:
```

```
tan_original = vy/vx
```

```
tan_revised = (tan_original - tan_theta) / (1 + tan_original * tan_theta)
```

```
vx = s / (1 + tan_revised**2)**0.5
```

```
vy = s * tan_revised / (1 + tan_revised**2)**0.5
```

```
if vx == 0:
```

```
vx = math.sin(theta) * s
```

```
vy = math.cos(theta) * s
```

```
# Vectorize acceleration
```

```
# (7) TODO : Explain the role of the if statements below ## Separate cases based on which  
wall the ball will collide with according to its velocity direction
```

$ax = a * (vx / s)$ if s else 0.0

$ay = a * (vy / s)$ if s else 0.0

if ($vx > 0$):

Collision at $W-r$

Calculation: $p + v * t - 0.5 * a * t^{**2} = W-r$ # Quadratic equation with scalar coefficients

Rearranged equation: $0.5 * a * t^{**2} - v * t + (W-r-p) = 0$

$tx = \text{min_root_from_eq_with_range}([0.5*ax, -vx, W-r-px], \text{inf})$

elif ($vx < 0$):

Collision at $0+r$

Rearranged equation: $0.5 * a * t^{**2} - v * t + (0+r-p) = 0$

$tx = \text{min_root_from_eq_with_range}([0.5*ax, -vx, r-px], \text{inf})$

else:

No collision in the x-direction

$tx = \text{inf}$

if ($vy > 0$):

$ty = \text{min_root_from_eq_with_range}([0.5*ay, -vy, H-r-py], \text{inf})$

elif ($vy < 0$):

This ball collides at $0+r$!

Rearranged equation: $0.5 * a * t^{**2} - v * t + (0+r-p) = 0$

$ty = \text{min_root_from_eq_with_range}([0.5*ay, -vy, r-py], \text{inf})$

else:

```

# No collision in the x-direction

ty = inf

if tx < ty: # x Collision

    return tx, "x"

else: # y Collision

    return ty, "y"

# Test code

ball_test = Ball(1,1,1,0, 0, "white")

ball_test.move(2)

# print(time_to_wall_collision(ball_test))

def time_to_ball_ball_collision(ball1, ball2): # When will ball1 and ball2 collide?

    # (p_final_x_1 - p_final_x_2)**2 + (p_final_y_1 - p_final_y_2)**2 = 2*r**2

# Retrieve values from the class

px1 = ball1.px

py1 = ball1.py

vx1 = ball1.vx

vy1 = ball1.vy

d1 = ball1.d

px2 = ball2.px

py2 = ball2.py

vx2 = ball2.vx

```

```
vy2 = ball2.vy
```

```
d2 = ball2.d
```

```
# Norm of velocity, speed, hypotenuse for trigonometry
```

```
s1 = (vx1 ** 2 + vy1 ** 2) ** 0.5
```

```
s2 = (vx2 ** 2 + vy2 ** 2) ** 0.5
```

```
# Recalculate velocity components based on the contact point
```

```
if d1 != 0:
```

```
    theta1 = N*abs(d1)**(0.5) * d1/abs(d1)
```

```
    tan_theta1 = math.tan(theta1)
```

```
    if vx1 != 0:
```

```
        tan_original1 = vy1/vx1
```

```
        tan_revised1 = (tan_original1 - tan_theta1) / (1 + tan_original1 * tan_theta1)
```

```
        vx1 = s1 / (1 + tan_revised1**2)**0.5
```

```
        vy1 = s1 * tan_revised1 / (1 + tan_revised1**2)**0.5
```

```
    if vx1 == 0:
```

```
        vx1 = math.sin(theta1) * s1
```

```
        vy1 = math.cos(theta1) * s1
```

```
if d2 != 0:
```

```
    theta2 = N*abs(d2)**(0.5) * d2/abs(d2)
```

```
    tan_theta2 = math.tan(theta2)
```

```
    if vx2 != 0:
```

$$\tan_original2 = v_{y2}/v_{x2}$$

$$\tan_revised2 = (\tan_original2 - \tan_theta2) / (1 + \tan_original2 * \tan_theta2)$$

$$v_{x2} = s2 / (1 + \tan_revised2**2)**0.5$$

$$v_{y2} = s2 * \tan_revised2 / (1 + \tan_revised2**2)**0.5$$

if $v_{x2} == 0$:

$$v_{x2} = \mathit{math}.\sin(\theta2) * s2$$

$$v_{y2} = \mathit{math}.\cos(\theta2) * s2$$

Vectorize acceleration; in this function, defined in the opposite direction of velocity

$$a_{x1} = -a * (v_{x1} / s1) \text{ if } s1 \text{ else } 0.0$$

$$a_{y1} = -a * (v_{y1} / s1) \text{ if } s1 \text{ else } 0.0$$

$$a_{x2} = -a * (v_{x2} / s2) \text{ if } s2 \text{ else } 0.0$$

$$a_{y2} = -a * (v_{y2} / s2) \text{ if } s2 \text{ else } 0.0$$

(8) TODO : Fill in the equations below

$$A_{2x} = 0.5 * a_{x1} - 0.5 * a_{x2} \text{ \# TODO}$$

$$A_{1x} = v_{x1} - v_{x2} \text{ \# TODO}$$

$$A_{0x} = p_{x1} - p_{x2} \text{ \# TODO}$$

$$A_{2y} = 0.5 * a_{y1} - 0.5 * a_{y2} \text{ \# TODO}$$

$$A_{1y} = v_{y1} - v_{y2} \text{ \# TODO}$$

$$A_{0y} = p_{y1} - p_{y2} \text{ \# TODO}$$

```
k4 = A2x**2 + A2y**2 # TODO
```

```
k3 = 2*A2x*A1x + 2*A2y*A1y # TODO
```

```
k2 = A1x**2 + 2*A2x*A0x + A1y**2 + 2*A2y*A0y # TODO
```

```
k1 = 2*A1x*A0x + 2*A1y*A0y # TODO
```

```
k0 = A0x**2 + A0y**2 - (2*r)**2 # TODO
```

```
t = min_root_from_eq_with_range([k4, k3, k2, k1, k0], inf)
```

```
return t
```

```
# Test run
```

```
ball_w = Ball(1,1,1,0,0, "white")
```

```
ball_r = Ball(2,1,-1,0,0.1, "red")
```

```
ball_y = Ball(2,2,-1,1,-0.7, "yellow")
```

```
print(time_to_ball_ball_collision(ball_w, ball_r))
```

```
print(time_to_ball_ball_collision(ball_w, ball_y))
```

```
def simulate(b1, b2, b3, b2_col, b3_col, b2_b3_col):
```

```
    # Calculate the trajectories of all three balls until they stop. Use the ball.move(t) function to
    compute movement and conveniently record the positions. Later, plot the trajectories as lines.
```

```
    # If balls collide, record the collision coordinates in ball_w_r_col and ball_w_y_col. Later,
    plot the collision points as black X markers.
```

```
while(b1.vx>0 or b1.vy>0 or b2.vx>0 or b2.vy>0 or b3.vx>0 or b3.vy>0):
```

```
    print("-----")
```

```

print(b1, " | ", b2, " | ", b3)

# (9) TODO: Add comments

# TODO : Time it takes for each ball to stop

t_b1_stop = time_stop(b1) if (b1.vx>0 or b1.vy>0) else inf
t_b2_stop = time_stop(b2) if (b2.vx>0 or b2.vy>0) else inf
t_b3_stop = time_stop(b3) if (b3.vx>0 or b3.vy>0) else inf

# TODO : Time until each ball collides with wall

t_b1_wall, b1_wall = time_to_wall_collision(b1)
t_b2_wall, b2_wall = time_to_wall_collision(b2)
t_b3_wall, b3_wall = time_to_wall_collision(b3)

# TODO : Time until each pair of balls collides

t_b1_b2_col = time_to_ball_ball_collision(b1, b2)
t_b1_b3_col = time_to_ball_ball_collision(b1, b3)
t_b2_b3_col = time_to_ball_ball_collision(b2, b3)

# TODO : All possible cases

t_list = [t_b1_stop, t_b2_stop, t_b3_stop, t_b1_wall, t_b2_wall, t_b3_wall, t_b1_b2_col,
t_b1_b3_col, t_b2_b3_col]

#print(t_list)

t_min = min(t_list)

print(t_list.index(t_min), t_list)

```

```
# TODO : Move each ball for the minimum time

b1.move(t_min)

b2.move(t_min)

b3.move(t_min)

# TODO : Case when a ball stops without any collision

if (t_min == t_b1_stop or t_min == t_b2_stop or t_min == t_b3_stop):

    if t_min == t_b1_stop:

        print("b1 stop")

        b1.vx = 0

        b1.vy = 0

    if t_min == t_b2_stop:

        print("b2 stop")

        b2.vx = 0

        b2.vy = 0

    if t_min == t_b3_stop:

        print("b3 stop")

        b3.vx = 0

        b3.vy = 0

    pass

# TODO : Case when a ball collides with a wall

elif (t_min == t_b1_wall):

    print("b1_wall")
```

```
if (b1_wall == 'x'):
    b1.vx = - b1.vx * K_ball_wall_col
    b1.vy = b1.vy * K_ball_wall_col
else:
    b1.vy = - b1.vy * K_ball_wall_col
    b1.vx = b1.vx * K_ball_wall_col
elif (t_min == t_b2_wall):
    print("b2_wall")
    if (b2_wall == 'x'):
        b2.vx = - b2.vx * K_ball_wall_col
        b2.vy = b2.vy * K_ball_wall_col
    else:
        b2.vy = - b2.vy * K_ball_wall_col
        b2.vx = b2.vx * K_ball_wall_col
elif (t_min == t_b3_wall):
    print("b3_wall")
    if (b3_wall == 'x'):
        b3.vx = - b3.vx * K_ball_wall_col
        b3.vy = b3.vy * K_ball_wall_col
    else:
        b3.vy = - b3.vy * K_ball_wall_col
        b3.vx = b3.vx * K_ball_wall_col
# TODO : Case when two balls collide
```

```

elif (t_min == t_b1_b2_col):

    print("W-R collision")

    b1.vx, b2.vx = b2.vx * K_ball_ball_col, b1.vx * K_ball_ball_col

    b1.vy, b2.vy = b2.vy * K_ball_ball_col, b1.vy * K_ball_ball_col

    b2_col.append([(b1.px + b2.px)/2, (b1.py + b2.py)/2])

elif (t_min == t_b1_b3_col):

    print("W-Y collision")

    b1.vx, b3.vx = b3.vx * K_ball_ball_col, b1.vx * K_ball_ball_col

    b1.vy, b3.vy = b3.vy * K_ball_ball_col, b1.vy * K_ball_ball_col

    b3_col.append([(b1.px + b3.px)/2, (b1.py + b3.py)/2])

elif (t_min == t_b2_b3_col):

    print("Y-R collision")

    b2.vx, b3.vx = b3.vx * K_ball_ball_col, b2.vx * K_ball_ball_col

    b2.vy, b3.vy = b3.vy * K_ball_ball_col, b2.vy * K_ball_ball_col

    b2_b3_col.append([(b2.px + b3.px)/2, (b2.py + b3.py)/2])

else:

    print("else")

```

----- Visualization Code -----

```

plt.figure(figsize=(9, 4.5))

plt.plot([0, W, W, 0, 0], [0, 0, H, H, 0], "g-")

```

```

for ball in (b1, b2, b3):

```

```

plt.plot(ball.px_log, ball.py_log,      # Trajectory line
         color=ball.color, lw=1.8)

plt.scatter(ball.px_log[-1], ball.py_log[-1], # Final position
            marker="^", s=80,
            color=ball.color, zorder=4)

for x, y in b2_col:                    # W-R collision coordinates
    plt.scatter(x, y, marker="x", color=b2.color,
               s=70, zorder=5)

for x, y in b3_col:                    # W-Y collision coordinates
    plt.scatter(x, y, marker="x", color=b3.color,
               s=70, zorder=5)

for x, y in b2_b3_col:                 # R-Y collision coordinates
    plt.scatter(x, y, marker="x", color=b1.color,
               s=70, zorder=5)

plt.gca().set_aspect("equal", adjustable="box")

plt.title("3-Ball Simulation")

plt.xlabel("X (m)")

plt.ylabel("Y (m)")

plt.xlim(-0.05, W + 0.05)

plt.ylim(-0.05, H + 0.05)

plt.show()

```

```
# Final Run 1
```

```
pwx, pwy, vwx, vwy, dw = (0,0,700,80, 0)
```

```
prx, pry, vrx, vry, dr = (70,40,0,0,0)
```

```
pyx, pyy, vyx, vyy, dy = (50,10,0,0,0)
```

```
ball_white = Ball(pwx, pwy, vwx, vwy, dw, "grey")
```

```
ball_red = Ball(prx, pry, vrx, vry, dr, "red")
```

```
ball_yellow = Ball(pyx, pyy, vyx, vyy, dy, "yellow")
```

```
ball_w_r_col = []
```

```
ball_w_y_col = []
```

```
ball_r_y_col = []
```

```
simulate(ball_white, ball_red, ball_yellow, ball_w_r_col, ball_w_y_col, ball_r_y_col)
```

```
# Final Run 2
```

```
pwx, pwy, vwx, vwy, dw = (0,0,770,110, 0.5)
```

```
prx, pry, vrx, vry, dr = (70,40,0,0,0)
```

```
pyx, pyy, vyx, vyy, dy = (50,10,0,0,0)
```

```
ball_white = Ball(pwx, pwy, vwx, vwy, dw, "grey")
```

```
ball_red = Ball(prx, pry, vrx, vry, dr, "red")
```

```

ball_yellow = Ball(pyx, pyy, vyx, vyy, dy, "yellow")

ball_w_r_col = []

ball_w_y_col = []

ball_r_y_col = []

simulate(ball_white, ball_red, ball_yellow, ball_w_r_col, ball_w_y_col, ball_r_y_col)

```

However, the results produced in this way had several unrealistic aspects. For example, the rotation of the balls was not considered, the reduction of speed after hitting a wall was not reflected, and the sliding of the ball immediately after being struck with the cue (before it starts rolling) was not captured. To address the biggest issue—the ball’s rotation—I attempted to approximate it as realistically as possible. First, I divided the factors determining ball rotation into two main elements: the contact point and the force of the strike. Then, I expressed the rotation applied to the ball as a function of these two factors. Specifically, I defined the contact point d as the horizontal distance from the center of the ball to the left or right, and I set the range of striking force from 0 to 50 N.

Next, let θ be the angle deviation from the ball’s original trajectory. I considered that θ caused by the contact point and the force would affect the trajectory differently in three cases: normal trajectory, trajectory after wall collision, and trajectory after ball collision. Therefore, I expressed each of these three cases with simple functions. Considering proportionality, inverse proportionality, and cases with no effect, the combined formulas for contact point and force became:

- Trajectory: $\theta = N\sqrt{d}$
- Wall collision: $\theta = M \frac{d^2}{F}$
- Ball collision: $\theta = K \cdot F$

I incorporated these formulas into the full code and applied simple approximations—such as multiplying by small damping constants—to handle other relatively minor effects.

Figure 3. Previous Results

As a result, the ball's movement after incorporating these adjustments appeared as shown in Figure 4. as opposed to the previous results shown in Figure 3.

Figure 4. Results after incorporating adjustments

Works Cited

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